

Intelligence to Please: An Interrogation of the Politicization of Intelligence Estimates

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19343916>

Citation: Equere, P. S., Ekong, I. E., & Antia, A. I. (2026). Intelligence to Please: An Interrogation of the Politicization of Intelligence Estimates. *Transnational Journal of Arts, Humanities and Sciences*, 2(1).

Abstract

Within the intelligence community, there are cases of intelligence politicization, which are complex phenomena that affect the credibility of intelligence. Scholarship on intelligence suggests that politicization occurs when intelligence analysis is either deliberately or inadvertently skewed to give policymakers the result they want, not the unvarnished truth about the situation at hand. For intelligence analysts and managers, politicization is considered a moral sin, a fundamental violation of their commitment to provide policymakers with honest answers and estimates. The intelligence community is supposed to be isolated from the political fray so that analysts and managers can tell policymakers the truth without fear of recrimination, no matter how unpleasant or politically damaging the truth might be to policymakers. This paper is an inquiry into the dynamics of politicization of intelligence. This paper views the politicization of intelligence estimates as a significant threat to the core of intelligence and its significance in policymaking. Using the analytical method of historical writing and relying mainly on secondary sources, the paper identifies and analyzes the conditions that breed intelligence politicization and suggests conditions or

measures necessary for intelligence agencies to provide policymakers with estimates that are not designed simply to support them in their partisan politics. The paper submits that analysts should not meddle in politics, and policymakers should not ask or force the analysts to 'cook the book'. To prevent bias in their work, intelligence analysts should avoid close relationships with policymakers to prevent their political agendas from influencing the analysis. They must maintain their objectivity if their estimates are to have the expected value.

Keywords: intelligence politicization, intelligence community, intelligence analysis, policymakers, objectivity.

Introduction

The term 'politicization' has many meanings and connotations, but the primary meaning is that when an issue is politicized, such an issue becomes contentious among political groups. Also, competing ideologies or preferred values become part of role definitions or policy choices in the processes of politicization. Another aspect of politicization is popularization or publicity, which can generate public debate over ends and means. A matter is politicized when it becomes involved in public policy choices and the ordering of power. Here, politicization of intelligence estimates refers to conditions external to the bureaucracy. Another form of politicization occurs when intelligence estimates are influenced by inherent policy positions. When preferred policies dominate decision-making, overt pressures are applied to intelligence systems, resulting in self-fulfilling intelligence prophecies or 'intelligence to please'. Knowledge can convey political power, and an agency of government charged with collecting secret information overseas and supplying knowledge to decision-makers will be drawn into politics. In this wise, politics and intelligence are subjected to an interrelationship.ⁱ

Politicization is a charge often leveled when intelligence estimates actually support one political position over another. In other words, when intelligence analysts hit their marks and produce timely finished intelligence that addresses matters of national importance and debate, charges are sometimes raised that someone has unduly influenced their intelligence process or that analysts are following their own policy or political agenda at the expense of objectivity.ⁱⁱ According to Richard Betts:

For issues of high importance and controversy, any relevant analysis is performed politically charged, because it points to a policy condition. Various disputes such as those about which elements of information are correct, ambiguous, or false; which of them are important, incidental, or irrelevant; in which context they should be understood, and against which varieties of information pointing in a different direction they would assess, are in effect, if not in intent, disputes about which policy conclusion stands or falls.ⁱⁱⁱ

Because intelligence estimates are inherently credible, individuals who oppose findings that are adverse to their political position have to attack the objectivity of the intelligence process, not the inherent validity of the analysis. When intelligence estimates have a political impact and help shape policy, the very goal of the intelligence community include some people interpreting that effect as evidence that the process must have been corrupted to serve political ends.

A variation of this phenomenon occurs when analysts complain when their estimates are ignored by policymakers. This situation usually occurs when analysts warn policymakers of impending policy failure or indicate that past estimates were inaccurate and in need of significant revision. There are a variety of reasons that policymakers might choose not to act on specific estimates. They might have information from other sources that provides different perspectives on current issues, or they might believe the effort to utilize the intelligence by changing policy might create more problems than one solves. In this sense, analysts break the grand bargain inherent in the relationship between the intelligence community and policymakers by going public in an effort to use estimates to shape policy.

This paper interrogates how politicization occurs within the intelligence community. The paper asserts that politicization is somehow inherent in the production of intelligence because information is vital to gaining and preserving political power. The paper aligns with the view of Harry Ransom that intelligence politicization is not an anomaly but a conventional relationship that emerges between policymakers and intelligence analysts.^{iv} The paper identifies, highlights, and explains the conditions necessary for intelligence organizations to provide policymakers with estimates that are not designed simply to support decision-makers in line with their partisan interests. To achieve this goal, the paper is structured in three parts. Part one identifies the sources of intelligence politicization, while part two highlights and explains in detail some case studies of intelligence politicization. Part three is the concluding remarks.

Sources of Intelligence Politicization

Although politicization can take a variety of forms, the paper focuses on three ways in which the production of finished intelligence can be corrupted by undue policy or political influence. These sources are pressure from policymakers, provision of subtle and not-so-subtle cues to intelligence managers, and skewing estimates to advance one's professional interests. The paper considers these sources in detail.

i. Corruption of Intelligence Process

One of the sources of politicization of intelligence is the pressure brought to bear on intelligent analysts by decision makers to emphasize findings that support their policies and preferences or to ignore issues that could cause political or personal embarrassment. Sometimes this pressure comes in direct requests to support existing policy because they are viewed by most observers as inherently credible and not influenced by the wishes of officials; intelligence findings can be used to terminate political debate or to gain political support. Thus, this type of politicization is best viewed as corruption of the intelligence process because intelligence analysts are considered politically detached observers and are supposed to stand above the political fray and provide honest estimates.^v

By contrast, other sources of politicization are produced by human frailty or organizational pathologies, not the direct manipulation of the intelligence process for political gain. Charges that the intelligence production had been subject to direct manipulation for political reasons emerged in the aftermath of the Second Gulf War in 2003 when conclusive evidence supporting the Bush administration claimed that Saddam Hussein's country had an active program to produce weapons of mass destruction, and a large stockpile of those weapons failed to materialize. Critics of the Bush administration in Iraq and in the international community claimed that worst-case thinking, if not outright manipulation, dominated the interpretation of every piece of evidence collected about Iraq's weapons program and that most of this spin was concocted by administration officials looking to justify military actions against the kleptocracy that engulfed Iraq.^{vi} Although some members of the intelligence community have suggested that the intelligence picture was far less conclusive than many administration officials suggested, most seem to stand by their general assessments of Iraq's overall desire to acquire and possess chemical, biological, and nuclear weapons. Analysts and diplomatic historians have asserted the justifications or otherwise of the Bush administration's pre-emptive attack on Iraq on the possessions

of weapons of mass destruction. Some have conjectured whether the cup was really “half full,” “half empty,” or “completely drained” in terms of Iraq’s chemical, biological, or nuclear capability, and exactly who was responsible for overselling the Iraqi weapons of mass destruction threat.^{vii}

ii. Provision of Subtle and Not-So-Subtle Cues to Intelligence Managers

Senior officials of the intelligence organizations such as the CIA sometimes give subtle and not so subtle cues to intelligence managers and analysts about the kind of analysis they welcome or abhor. If intelligence consumers fawn over or reward analysts who provide them with encouraging reports but dismiss, berate, or punish analysts who bring them disconcerting news, they will send a stinging signal to analysts everywhere. Analysts will line up to provide consumers with positive estimates that shrink from the prospect of reporting bad news. Given the nature of leadership within the intelligence community, only the most intractable problems and disputes are resolved at the top of the bureaucratic hierarchy, it takes an exceptional official to welcome the receipt of another negative report and to thank the bearer of bad news. Exceptional leaders cultivate a reputation for demanding the untarnished truth from their staff, and they make sure that just the bearers of good news are recognized for outstanding efforts.^{viii} A good example of this form of politicization of intelligence occurred during the Vietnam War. General William Westmoreland, the commander of American Military Assistance Command, had asked his military historians to produce a study of sieges throughout recorded history to generate some insights into the North Vietnamese effort to overwhelm the American Marine Firebase at Khe Sanh, which was located just below the demilitarized zone that separated North from South Vietnam. The military historians were asked to study the matter and deliver a briefing to the American troops.^{ix}

After describing the various wars that had occurred, the historians concluded that the news was not good for the marines. Most besieged fortresses fell because the attacker retained mobility. Needless to say, the news shocked the officers that were present at the briefing. At the end of the briefing, General Westmoreland thanked the historians for their report and turned to his troops, saying that now that they had heard the worst-case assessment, they would no longer tolerate anyone thinking, planning, or acting as if the siege of Khe Sanh would end in defeat. Whatever his motives were, Westmoreland virtually guaranteed that whoever was in that hall that day would think twice before bringing the boss bad news in the future.^x

iii. Estimates to Advance Professional Interests

Analysts can skew their intelligence estimates to advance their professional interests, attack their personal or professional rivals, or simply advance their careers. They can ignore negative trends or mistakes, especially if they are about to transfer into another organization to receive a promotion. It is better to leave one's position on a high note than to draw negative attention to problems that can jeopardize an otherwise positive record, especially at critical times. No news is always good news to those in charge of running a large organization; deciding not to rock the bureaucratic boat rarely damages one's career prospects.^{xi}

Politicization in this sense is really a form of careerism. Analysts and intelligence managers place greater emphasis on enhancing their job prospects than on fulfilling their responsibilities and personal interests. This occurs when analysts' findings call into question the performance or policies of their home organization or institution. Making senior officials aware of analysis that undermines the preferences or priorities of one's home institution is fraught with professional danger, and few people will persevere in the face of opposition from virtually everyone they encounter in the workplace. For example, John McCone's performance as the director of American Central Intelligence in the months leading to the Cuban Missile Crisis provides an outstanding example of someone who did not allow concerns about his interests and reputation to get in the way of his responsibilities. During the summer of 1962, a consensus emerged among CIA analysts that it was unlikely that the Soviets would place offensive missiles in Cuba, and this finding was reported officially to policymakers in a Special National Intelligence Estimate. McCone became increasingly concerned about the possibility that the United States might suffer some sort of intelligence failure related to Cuba, as the Soviets attempted to hoard their activities on the island in secrecy.^{xii}

Despite the CIA's official estimate, an estimate that was reported to the most senior official in the Kennedy administration, McCone pushed agency analysts to repeatedly reassess their judgment about the Soviets' activities in Cuba. McCone was less concerned about his reputation or his agency's track record for being correct and more interested in preventing the president from being caught by surprise by some nefarious intelligence schemes.^{xiii}

Case Studies of Intelligence Politicization

There are several examples of intelligence politicization that demonstrate that, because knowledge is power and politics is fundamentally about the exercise of power, intelligence estimates and operations often become deeply entangled in policy and political processes. This can happen in different ways. Accordingly, this paper examines three cases: American intelligence estimates of the Communist enemy in Vietnam, estimates of Soviet strategic power and intentions, and the estimates that contributed to intelligence failure in Iran. These cases are analyzed in detail, beginning with Vietnam.

i. Intelligence Estimate and the Nature and Size of the Forces in Vietnam

Between 1966 and 1967, a controversy came up within the American intelligence community about the nature and size of the Communist forces in Vietnam. Details of this dispute were first exposed in 1965, when Sam Adams, a former CIA analyst, published an article in Harper's Magazine, asserting that the military command in Vietnam had deliberately misrepresented the size of communist forces in South Vietnam. In essence, the CIA estimates of enemy strength were nearly twice those officially estimated by the American Military Assistance Command led by George William Westmoreland between 1964 and 1968, and other officials rejected civilian intelligence estimates, arguing that the CIA estimates included insurgent groups having no substantial military capacity, which were not classifiable as 'fighters.'

This dispute went to the heart of American strategy in Vietnam, based as it was upon the goal of attrition and of gradually reducing the enemy's capability and will to pursue its revolution. The Vietnam War remains a controversial issue for debate among historians and foreign policy analysts. Was the administration's and Westmoreland's strategy based upon inaccurate calculations? Was this a colossal intelligence blunder? Was the president deliberately misled by the military officials wanting to send encouraging news? If the CIA's pessimism rather than the military's more optimistic stance had prevailed, would the United States have withdrawn from the war sooner? Was there a conspiracy at the highest levels of American military intelligence to suppress and alter critical intelligence on the enemy in the year leading up to the Tet offensive?^{xiv}

To complete this complex intelligence issue as a simple question: were the military intelligence figures manipulated to anticipate the presumed taste of political leaders at home, in which case one sees intelligence politicized to a major degree, or

was this simply a case of varying judgments about the capabilities and intentions of an enemy? During the lengthy trial between October 1984 and February 1985, in which General Westmoreland sued CBS for libel as a result of its television documentary arguing that the General had engaged in a conspiracy to falsify enemy strength for political purposes, a revealing amount of testimony in the Westmoreland and CBS trial tended to support the argument that the military had in effect imposed a ceiling, determined by concern with politics at home, on estimates of enemy strength. But no conclusive evidence was presented in the trial that the military estimates were deliberately tailored for political purposes.

There is no doubt from the record that the administration and military officials in the field feared that a demonstration of a lack of military progress by the American forces in South Vietnam would aid the growing number of opponents of the war. Throughout the summer and fall of 1967, elaborate efforts were made to produce compromise estimates that would bring together CIA and military differences.^{xv} The thrust of the argument was that throughout the debate over enemy strength, the president and his advisers were attempting to rally public and congressional support for the war by demonstrating progress and encouraging hope for a successful ending in the near future. The simple fact was that estimates showing an increased enemy military strength, however calculated, stood in the way of demonstrating "light at the end of the tunnel." General Westmoreland knew that the political leadership hoped for and public opinion demanded good news. The CIA's estimates of greater enemy strength were bad news.^{xvi}

On January 30, 1968, the North Vietnamese Communists launched what is now known as the Tet Offensive, coordinated attacks against every major city in South Vietnam. Communist soldiers were pictured on American home television screens inside the American Embassy building in Saigon. Even though the ultimate outcome of the Tet Offensive, surprising in its velocity and scope, was militarily catastrophic for North Vietnam, the Viet Cong earned the decisive victory of the war by winning a spectacular psychological victory over American public opinion. The public had been fed a heavy diet of optimism, encouragement, and progress reports by its military and civilian leadership, and suddenly the enemy appeared to be strong enough to attack on all fronts.

The Vietnam War shattered the image of American progress and hopes for an early conclusion to the war. The Tet Offensive reopened the 'Order of Battle' dispute among civilian and military intelligence analysts. By March of 1968, CIA estimates of

total Communist military and guerrilla forces in South Vietnam charged as high as 600,000, a figure which many military men found incredible. CIA officials for their part suspected that the military estimates continued to be tailored for political purposes. No real agreement was ever reached by the contending sides, despite great efforts to achieve compromise.

Indeed, no agreement on the issues exists today, as evidenced by earnest testimony by both sides in Westmoreland's unsuccessful libel suit against CBS. If Westmoreland did not win, neither did CBS, which, in effect, settled out of court without final and convincing validation of its conspiracy hyperbole. The question of how to count the enemy's strength was a perplexing intelligence problem in the Vietnam War. Whatever the truth in the matter, the case demonstrates the interrelatedness of intelligence and policy and the inevitable interactions, in a free society not fighting a consensus war, of intelligence and politics.^{xvii}

ii. Estimating Soviet Military Power

Another example demonstrating the confluence of ideology, politics, and intelligence is estimates of Soviet military power. The case of Westmoreland and CBS demonstrated the alleged military conspiracy to underestimate enemy strength for domestic political purposes. The so-called "Team B" episode illustrates the effort of the military and their allies to engage in a "worst-case" estimate of Soviet military strength in order to influence policy.

The CIA was established to institutionalize the intelligence ethic of policy neutrality. The State Department at the Pentagon, with all their experts on foreign and military matters and with their separate intelligence staff, were expected to be policy advocates. In pursuit of objectivity, the Board of National Estimates was a totally independent staff arm; the individual analysts drafting estimates in theory worked behind the protective walls of policy independence, detached from partisan or vested interests pressure. Ultimately, the Board of Estimates and its staff were abolished in 1973 for many reasons. Perhaps most important was that independent national estimates limited the policy options of activist decision-makers. In other words, the facts sometimes got in the way of what the leadership wanted to do. Henry Kissinger put it in this way. "In my experience, the CIA developed the basis for my inaction much more frequently than for daring thrust."

More of the points were criticism that the CIA record in predicting accurately the development of Soviet strategic military forces was poor. Senator Malcolm Wallop reviewed his perception of the record in 1978 as follows:

While the Soviets were beginning the biggest military buildup in history, the National Intelligence Estimate judged that they would not try to build up as many missiles as we had. When the Soviets approached our number, the NIE said they would not try for decisive superiority and the capability to fight and win a nuclear war. Only very recently has the NIE admitted the possibility of an elusive question. Now the NIE says the Soviets may be trying for such a capability, but they cannot be sure it will work.

In place of the Board of National Estimates, the position of National Intelligence Office was created in 1973. The NIO was to be responsible for producing a particular estimate. It was hoped that estimates would be sharper and less compromised to meet all views; that those in charge of estimates would be more specialized, focused, and accountable; and some would say that estimates are more relevant to, if not supportive of, policy concerns. Even with this reorganization, the estimates system came under sharp criticism from those who were convinced that the CIA was underestimating the development of Soviet strategic military capability. In 1975, during President Gerald Ford's administration, the President's Foreign Intelligence Advisory Board took issues with the CIA's general posture, suggesting that the Soviet Union was not superior militarily to the United States, nor was it seen as planning to wage and win a nuclear war. The PFIAB, weighted heavily with foreign policy hardliners, persuaded the then CIA Director to appoint a group of outsiders to evaluate the CIA estimates on Soviet military strength and come up with independent findings. After reviewing the CIA's estimates, this group known as 'Team B' concluded that the CIA (Team A) had systematically underestimated the strategic military capability of the Soviets. This came to be known as the "Team A – Team B Controversy." Controversy over Soviet estimates had been frequent within the American government circle for a quarter of a century. However, the appointment of an independent group was a novel and much-criticized move, since the independent group was in no way ideologically balanced. Indeed, it was a phalanx composed primarily of men who became leaders in the near future.

The Team B group ended up challenging the CIA's findings on Soviet strength, not so much on capabilities as on intentions. The group assumed that the Soviet was bent on world domination, was preparing to fight and win a nuclear war, had

undertaken a formidable civil defense effort, was aiming at nuclear superiority over the United States, and that a window of vulnerability confronted the American strategic force. It saw CIA analysts as caught up in “mirror-imaging” U.S. strategic posture and doctrine when estimating future windows of capabilities and intentions of the Soviets. The Team B episode demonstrated a novel way in which intelligence can be politicized. A minority view on Soviet power and intentions was foisted upon the intelligence system. What was missing was a Team C, made up of arms control enthusiasts with different assumptions about the Soviet's goals and capabilities. Former CIA director Stansfield Turner has provided a good summary of this episode, capped by some knowledgeable advice:

A new technique of competitive analysis was attempted in 1976. This was the so-called A-Team, B-Team competition. The analytic groups were organized to study U.S. and Soviet military capabilities. Team A was the CIA's normal analytic group on this subject. Team B was composed of outsiders with a right-wing ideological bent. The intention was to promote competition by polarizing the teams. It failed. The CIA team, knowing that the outsiders on B would take extreme views, tended to do so in self-defense. When Team-B felt frustrated over its inability to prevail, one of its members leaked much of the proceedings to the press. My reluctance to use this team approach was criticized, but I believe that putting extremists against one another can only lead to poor results. Instead, extremist views should be permitted to emerge from the analytic effort to be included as a minority view in the report.^{xviii}

The Team B episode illustrated one way in which intelligence can be politicized. However, this is not to suggest that politicization is inherently destructive of accurate intelligence. But if benefits exist in such a method of competitive intelligence, clearly there are also costs.

iii. Intelligence Failure in Iran: An Example of Politicization

In 1978, the CIA informed President Carter of the USA that the Shah of Iran, obviously buffeted by internal unrest, was secured in his position for the future. The Shah was deposed in an internal revolution shortly thereafter. Was this failure in forecasting the result of politicization? Was this an example of an intelligence agency offering the leadership “intelligence to please”? In 1978, President Carter had sincerely toasted the Shah as the head of ‘an island of stability in one of the most troubled areas of the world.’ In the words of Carter's national security adviser, “The fall of the Shah was clearly a political calamity for President Carter.”

The question begging for an answer is whether the intelligence system, realizing that this would be the case, was consciously or unconsciously influenced to forecast that such a calamity would not happen. Few argued the judgment that American comprehension of the political situation was a significant failure of intellect. Zbigniew Brzezinski recalled in his memoirs, "The intelligence system gave the President little preparation for the shock that the sudden disintegration of Iran was for him, as well as for the rest of us."

The case of the unexpected collapse of the Shah is an example of one type of intelligence politicization. Understanding the true nature of this failure with only limited access to the record is difficult. Various participants have supplied a variety of presumably self-serving memoirs. Fortunately, the staff of the American House of Representatives Select Committee on Intelligence undertook a study in late 1978 and issued a report in January 1979. The report was based on interviews with CIA managers and analysts, officials in the Department of State, the Defense Intelligence Agency, and the National Security Agency, and an analysis of current intelligence archives.^{xi} What emerges are some significant insights; these insights include the inadequacy of the collection and analysis of information from Iran and the anchoring of American foreign policy on the Shah's survival. The paper examines these insights in details.^{xx}

Inadequacy of Collection and Analysis of Information from Iran

Collection and analysis of information from Iran were inadequate. Reports of anti-Shah demonstrations were greeted with complacency in Washington. The power of the religious opposition, which later came to be the ruling group, was seriously underestimated. Also interpreted was the depth of popular, middle-class opposition to the Shah. The data flow from Iran was incomplete and misleading; its interpretation at intelligence headquarters was unsophisticated and complacent.

Anchoring the American Foreign Policy on Shah's Survival

The American foreign policy in the Persian Gulf region was anchored to the Shah's survival. A deliberate policy of no contact with opposition elements was in effect because of fears of antagonizing the Shah, who himself feared clandestine activities by the CIA within his realm. Policy makers were not asking the intelligence system to assess the strength of the Shah; they simply assumed that the Shah would prevail over opposition elements indefinitely. In sum, policymakers were consciously politicizing intelligence because American policy was firmly fixed on the assumption that the Shah

was secured; the decision-making system was incapable of absorbing information that would challenge such assumptions.^{xxi}

Intelligence papers were made available to decision makers on a daily basis at the White House for the President's eyes, noting the seriousness of disturbances in Iran. The White House reaction to such signals was not to ask for more detailed analysis of the Shah's stability. The question of removing the restriction that had been placed on CIA clandestine collection in Iran was not considered out of fear of displeasing the Shah.^{xxii} In other words, political leaders seemed to demand only good news from Iran. Intelligence agencies were prone unconsciously to report what they think or know leaders want to hear. Yet the intelligence system felt the sting of presidential displeasure after the event. President Carter in November 1978 penned a handwritten note to his national security adviser. With pointed reference to his surprise at events in Iran, he told them, "I am not satisfied with the quality of political intelligence." In his memoirs, Zbigniew Brzezinski takes credit for this presidential note. Quoting from his diary, he noted that he was "really appalled by how inept and vague Stan Turner's comments on the crisis in Iran were. This reinforces my strong view that we need much better political intelligence.

The question is, was Iran another case of intelligence failure, like Pearl Harbor and Korea, with world-shaking consequences? A simple but positive answer to this question may be misleading because it would ignore the role of policy and political leadership in the failure. It would also ignore the subtle ways intelligence becomes politicized by unquestioning policy assumptions. The verdict of the American House Select Committee on Intelligence seems valid. It found that:

In the case of Iran, long-standing U.S. attitudes toward the Shah inhibited intelligence collection, dampened policymakers' appetite for analysis of the Shah's position, and deafened policymakers to the warning implicit in available current intelligence.

Furthermore, the covert branch of the CIA (the Left Hand) put the Shah in power, and he was the CIA's man; the CIA was a principal booster of the Shah. However, the analytical branch of the CIA (The Right Hand) failed to provide policy-free information about the Shah's position. Such a system provided few incentives to challenge the conventional wisdom or to substitute facts for preferences. Stanfield Turner was in charge of the CIA during the Iranian crisis. In his memoirs, he analyzed the intelligence failure. He admitted that there were two fundamental factors that the Carter administration, as well as earlier administrations, had failed to identify. One was

the growing dissatisfaction with the Shah, and the other was the rising appeal of Islamic fundamentalism. There was a failure to see that a variety of dissident groups would coalesce under Khomeini. While dissidence was recognized, the primary failure was to assume that the Shah, who controlled a powerful army, police force, and ruthless secret intelligence service, would not be able to use these instruments of state power to maintain control. Turner's most telling comment was "U.S. policy in the area of the world was so dependent on the Shah that it was all too easy for us to assume that he would do what was necessary to play the role we had in mind for him."

Turner gives insights into other aspects of the intelligence failure regarding Iran. One aspect was that intelligence analysis lives in a ratified atmosphere where there is excessive emphasis on the use of secret data as opposed to open information. As a long-range trend, Turner noted that there was relatively little secret information that was relevant, and intelligence analysts tend to be disdainful of outside scholars as 'second opinions' from experts. Furthermore, the CIA was short on specialized analytic skills pertinent to Iran, particularly the skills of sociologists and anthropologists. Another factor was the inherent conservatism of a large bureaucracy. Turner suggested that more probability estimating would have been useful, but he found the bureaucracy resistant to innovative analytic methods.

Most importantly, Turner's experience led him to observe the following: The White House was repeatedly insensitive to the importance of protecting the political credibility of intelligence. It would seem clear that, however subtle, unconscious, and indirect, the White House had politicized intelligence and induced failure.^{xxiii}

Factors that Determines the Degree of Intelligence Politicization

Having discussed the case studies of intelligence politicization, this part of the paper examines the factors or variables that characterize the intelligence system at any given time. A number of variables have been identified that interacts to affect the degree of isolation from politics permitted for intelligence systems. These are:

i. The International Environment

A consensus about the ends and means of foreign policy will produce a setting in which an intelligence agency can adhere to its ideal of policy neutrality and of insulation from politics. The behavior of other states perceived as adversaries is one variable of the international environment that is an important conditioning factor. When a consensus

in perceiving the nature of the foreign threat breaks down or is weak, the intelligence system may be expected to lose its immunity from politicization.

ii. The State Political Culture

The state political culture, which interacts with the consensus perceptions of the external factors, is another variable that determines the degree of intelligence politicization. For example, Americans are ambivalent about secret agencies of government. Common assumptions about the threat of an external enemy move the shared value of the citizen's right to know in the direction of acceptance of secrecy and censorship. The greater the demand for openness and accountability in government, which increases during times of perceived peace, the likelihood of intelligence politicization also rises. When the Cold War consensus that lasted between 1947 and 1967 began to wane, so did the media and legislative reluctance to debate publicly intelligence policy, organizations, operations, and products. Put simply, in times when no national security emergency is perceived, it is the national tendency of the state political culture to politicize intelligence.

iii. The State Intelligence Architecture

The third factor or variable is the state intelligence structure. Internal bureaucratic conflict over turf as well as disagreement over estimates have characterized the intelligence system from the onset. But internal bureaucratic struggles, in which 'leaks' to the news media are sometimes a weapon, can quickly politicize intelligence, for it commonly leads to public debate over intelligence-related issues and often divides political parties or factions within parties. Executive-legislative separation of powers is an institutional invitation to intelligence politicization. The institutionalization of intelligence oversight in the Parliament permanently politicized intelligence, but the degree to which this is so will be influenced by the other factors aforementioned.

iv. Personality Factor

The idiosyncratic or personality factor is another important variable that determines intelligence politicization. This is so, particularly with regard to the personality of the man in charge of the state intelligence community. The generalissimo's personality, how he was chosen and appointed, his personal definition of role, perception, worldview, political and educational background, and ideological persuasion affect the degree of politicization of intelligence.

In sum, a behavioral generalization is that in times of consensus, war, "cold" or "hot," when national unity exists and political bipartisanship prevails, an intelligence

agency will come close to applying its doctrinal orthodoxy of policy neutrality. But when the varied interests of a plural society are at odds over the ends and means of foreign policy, particularly the means, the intelligence system tends to become politicized. In such a situation, the intelligence system is less likely to function at maximum efficiency.

The purpose of intelligence such as accurate information, promptly communicated, will most likely be fulfilled when:

- i. Executive–Legislative cooperation is genuine;
- ii. There is no weak link in the intelligence process chain;
- iii. The presidency is acutely sensitive to the dangers of a politicized intelligence system; and
- iv. The state political culture incorporates some understanding that the greatest threat to national security is a misinformed or ill-informed political leadership.

Conclusion

In this discourse, questions have been raised as to whether intelligence agencies were inevitably drawn into politics, whether the assignment of policy implementation (covert action) automatically politicizes, or whether policy neutrality is either a necessity or a reasonable expectation for intelligence agencies. The paper attempts to highlight the features of behavioral generalization, the abstract intelligence model of policy neutralism, with the observed reality of how things really work. Unquestionably, intelligence doctrine calls for policy neutrality in that crucial stage of the intelligence process of reporting the facts and making judgments about the unknown. The axiom that intelligence should be strictly separated from policy is hallowed. Nevertheless, the question is where exactly to draw the line separating intelligence and politics.

The intelligence community performs its idealized functions, reporting the facts even if it informs leaders that policy is wrong or not working, even if it causes domestic political problems or endangers the political security of the leadership in power. However, the CIA's intelligence record in Vietnam was not clear. The CIA was often in conflict with the military concerning order of battle figures (strength of the enemy). However, at crucial points, the CIA seems to have compromised with the military on the strength of the enemy for political rather than intelligence moves. The result was that at crucial periods of the Vietnam War, the strength of the enemy was underestimated by half.^{xxiv} It is the subject of politics in the sense that those seeking access to political power must gain access to information in the process. Information is

a key to power; it gives an advantage and provides the means for gaining power. Once power is attained, intelligence becomes the object for maintaining power. Intelligence must remain elusive, both in the domestic and international sense. Access to intelligence is strictly limited to those holding power. Maintenance of secrecy thus becomes an imperative, not just to persons exercising responsible political leadership (access to intelligence secrets is a primary basis of that power) but also to the state, which tries vigorously to maintain intelligence secrecy as a requirement of national security.

Intelligence is also an instrument of political power in the sense that agents of secret intelligence (spies) function in the dual role as agents of political influences. This became a major function of an intelligence agency, particularly when military power reached the stage of being too destructive to have political utility. This explains why the clandestine arm of the American CIA came to dominate the American intelligence community, especially during the Cold War years. Once an intelligence agency is called upon to implement foreign policy such as overthrowing an unfriendly government, conducting paramilitary operations, buying an election, or waging psychological warfare, the agency automatically becomes politicized; hence, neutrality becomes impossible.

In light of these arguments, this paper submits that intelligence is inextricably intertwined with politics so much that the intelligence agency uses it to carry out policy. It is a law of bureaucratic behavior as well as a universal tendency that agencies with operational responsibilities produce analyses that support their operating programs, and yet the doctrine of policy neutrality remains the compass or the guiding ethic of intelligence missions. The analytical challenge is to suggest when such doctrine will prevail and when it will be overcome by the political variables pressing upon it.^{xxv}

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